

MULTIDISCIPLINARY DESIGN AND OPTIMIZATION OF STRUT-BRACED HYBRID-ELECTRIC AIRCRAFT UNDER MULTI-TRAJECTORY SCENARIOS.

Pablo Norczyk Simon^{1*}, Rauno Cavallaro², Danlin Zheng Zhang³, Jānis Brižs⁴

1 - Barcelona Supercomputing Centre (BSC), Spain. pnorczyk@bsc.es

2 - Department of Aerospace Engineering, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, Spain
rauno.cavallaro@uc3m.es

3 - CRIDA A.I.E., Spain. dzheng@e-crida.enaire.es

4 - Riga Airport, Latvia. J.Brizs@riga-airport.com

Abstract. *Hybrid-electric aircraft offer a promising pathway for reducing aviation emissions, but integrating novel powerplant components and their mission-level control presents significant design challenges. This study employs a GEMSEO-based multidisciplinary optimization framework, to perform comprehensive sizing and optimization of the INDIGO aircraft—characterized by a high aspect ratio wing and distributed hybrid-electric propulsion optimized for reduced landing and takeoff (LTO) impact. The research evaluates optimization strategies across three scenarios: (1) single trajectory analysis, (2) multiple trajectories with a common control strategy, and (3) multiple trajectories with mission-specific control strategies. Results highlight the critical importance of multi-point analysis for achieving robust and reliable aircraft design. Although mission-specific control strategies provided more optimal outcomes, they also increased mission planning complexity. Furthermore, the study examines aircraft performance under five distinct failure scenarios, offering insights into the resilience and adaptability of hybrid-electric propulsion architectures. These findings contribute to a deeper understanding of optimization methodologies for emerging hybrid-electric aircraft configurations.*

Keywords: Multidisciplinary Optimization, INDIGO, Large Aspect Ration Wings, Local Air Quality, Noise, Distributed Hybrid Electric Aircraft

1 INTRODUCTION

Aviation stands at a critical juncture, facing the urgent need to decarbonize operations amid escalating environmental concerns. As of 2023, the sector accounted for approximately 2.5% of global CO₂ emissions [1], exhibiting the fastest emission growth rates among all transportation modes [2]. By 2050, the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) projects that, without decisive intervention, international aviation emissions could triple compared to 2015 levels [3]. This environmental urgency drives the exploration of innovative aircraft configurations aimed at minimizing aviation’s impact on emissions, Local Air Quality, and Noise (LAQN). The EU-funded INDIGO project [4] exemplifies such efforts, integrating Large Aspect Ratio Wings (LARW) with Distributed Hybrid Electric Propulsion (DHEP) to enhance efficiency and reduce environmental impact.

However, developing novel configurations is often a complex endeavor; with a lack of historical data and many disciplines often competing with each other, traditional methods are often unable to leverage the new technologies. Multidisciplinary Analysis and Optimization (MDAO) has emerged here as a transformative technology, enabling holistic design synthesis by simultaneously evaluating various aircraft systems and eliminating the need for manual iteration through complex trade-offs.

Although MDAO can substantially accelerate the aircraft design process, optimizing for single-point or single-trajectory scenarios frequently yields non-robust configurations that, while optimal at their design points, exhibit inferior performance under off-design conditions or prove unreliable for diverse mission profiles. This challenge becomes particularly critical when considering real-world aircraft operations, where inherent variability in trajectories—especially during initial climb and final descent phases across airports with different procedures—can result in designs over-fitted to specific scenarios.

This paper investigates the effects of various trajectories on hybridization and distributed propulsion strategies to perform a sensitivity analysis comparing single-mission versus multi-mission optimization approaches. The paper is structured as follows: first, we present the methodology for modeling the aircraft architecture, followed by an overview of the MDA framework. We then formulate the MDO problem statement, analyze the resulting data, and draw conclusions regarding optimal design strategies for robust hybrid aircraft configurations.

2 METHODOLOGY

In this paper, TOPAZ, a GEMSEO-based [5] MDAO framework for aircraft synthesis, is utilized. The framework develops aircraft synthesis capabilities comparable to other established codes such as OpenConcept [6], FastOAD [7], MOTIVATION [8] or Aviary [9]. Originally created with a special focus on mass distribution and internal volume allocation for novel configurations such as hydrogen-powered aircraft [10], TOPAZ performs comprehensive aircraft sizing through mission-performance evaluation—flying nominal and extended missions while assessing takeoff performance under various failure scenarios. This performance evaluation employs well-established handbook formulas and surrogate models. Additionally, the platform employs JAX [11] Automatic Differentiation within select disciplines through the GEMSEO-JAX plugin. The following section details the models used for aircraft optimization and the assessment of control strategies across various mission profiles.

Figure 1: Conceptual model of the INDIGO aircraft architecture.

2.1 The INDIGO Architecture

Funded by HORIZON Europe, the INDIGO project aims to improve Local Air Quality and Noise (LAQN) by developing a novel mid-range aircraft designed for 1000 nm route operations. The concept, illustrated in Fig. 1, achieves these improvements through aerodynamic enhancements featuring strut-braced, high aspect ratio wings, and a cutting-edge parallel-serial propulsion architecture. This architecture combines turboshaft engines operating in parallel with distributed electric propulsion units arranged along the wing in a serial configuration.

The Airbus A320neo serves as the reference aircraft for the INDIGO project. Accordingly, the INDIGO aircraft is designed to carry an equivalent payload weight, W_{PL} , of 20 tons with a maximum takeoff weight (MTOW) of 79 tons. The cabin layout replicates that of the A320neo, accommodating 180 passengers in a single-class economy configuration [12].

2.1.1 Aerodynamic performance estimation

For aerodynamic performance estimation, the platform employs a classical drag polar with linearized lift and pitching moment coefficients (Eq.1a, Eq.1b, Eq.1c), comprising 11 coefficients that capture the first and second-order dependencies with angle of attack α (denoted by the subscripts α and $\alpha\alpha$), first and second-order dependencies with elevator deflection δ_e (denoted by the subscripts δ_e and $\delta_e\delta_e$) and values at zero incidence (denoted by the subscript 0). These aircraft-level coefficients are derived by aggregating individual fitted surfaces (wing and tail for lift and drag, with fuselage, fairings, and vertical tail contributing to drag).

$$C_L = C_{L_0} + \alpha \cdot C_{L_\alpha} + \delta_e \cdot C_{L_{\delta_e}} \quad (1a)$$

$$C_D = C_{D_0} + \alpha \cdot (C_{D_\alpha} + \alpha \cdot C_{D_{\alpha\alpha}}) + \delta_e \cdot (C_{D_{\delta_e}} + \delta_e \cdot C_{D_{\delta_e\delta_e}}) \quad (1b)$$

$$C_M = C_{M_0} + \alpha \cdot C_{M_\alpha} + \delta_e \cdot C_{M_{\delta_e}} \quad (1c)$$

The polar coefficients for the wing are obtained through a surrogate model of a strut-braced wing trained with optimal wing designs. The training dataset is generated by performing aerodynamic shape optimizations using VSPAERO [13]. Each optimization

Figure 2: Top: normalized lift distribution across the wingspan for an $AR = 22$. Bottom left: reconstructed aerodynamic polars from $AR = 4$ to $AR = 26$ in $\Delta AR = 2$ increments; in marker, values at direct VSPAERO executions. Bottom right: maximum aerodynamic efficiency (AE) and C_L at that point obtained from the reconstructed polars.

is performed at a fixed aspect ratio (AR) using a parametric model composed of a main wing and a supporting strut. The main wing features a constant chord up to the mid-section ($y = b/4$), beyond which it tapers at a constant taper ratio (λ_w). The strut has a constant chord equal to 0.5 times the wing root chord. Design variables for these discipline-level optimizations include wing twists at the root $\theta_{w,y=0}$, mid $\theta_{w,y=b/4}$ and tip section $\theta_{w,y=b/2}$, the strut twist the root $\theta_{w,y=0}$ and the outer wing taper ratio λ_w . Subsequently, the coefficients C_{L_0} , C_{L_α} , C_{D_0} , C_{D_α} , $C_{D_{\alpha\alpha}}$ from each optimized configuration are fitted across AR for system-level optimization. This methodology emulates a bi-level approach, with the inner discipline-level design variables remaining hidden from the system-level optimization, which only manages the AR . Fig.2 illustrates the resultant optimized lift distributions and aerodynamic polars of each optimized wing.

For the horizontal tail, vortex drag is calculated using classical methods such as DATCOM [14]. Parasite drag for the fuselage, horizontal tail, and vertical tail is determined using drag breakdown coefficients from established sources [15–18]. Downwash estimation assumes an elliptical lift distribution to decouple wing and tail coefficients. While this assumption may not apply to all wing platforms, the near-elliptical distributions achieved through optimization (Fig. 2) support its validity. To ensure proper tail sizing, the model calculates the neutral point and static margin at each flight phase, following the methodology previously implemented in [10].

Figure 3: Definition of the parallel-serial configuration for the INDIGO aircraft.

2.1.2 Powerplant component modeling

The INDIGO powerplant architecture comprises two components: an inboard parallel system and an outboard serial electric propulsion system. The inboard parallel system features an inboard propeller connected to a gearbox operated by a turboshaft engine and an electric machine. This electric machine can function both as an electric motor (supplying power to the gearbox) and as a generator (drawing power from the gearbox). To manage the power split between the gas turbine and the electric machine, a local hybridization factor HF^* is introduced. The powers provided by the turboshaft and the electric machine are expressed as shown in Eq. 3. For positive hybridization values ($HF^* \in [1, 0]$), the electric machine acts as a motor, delivering additional power to assist the propeller. For negative values ($HF^* \in [0, -\infty]$), the electric machine acts as a generator, extracting mechanical power from the turboshaft to support the electrical system

$$P_{A,gb} = P_{out,gb} \cdot (1 - HF^*) \quad , \quad P_{B,gb} = P_{out,gb} \cdot HF^* \quad (2)$$

For the outboard serial system, eight Electric Propulsion Units (EPUs) are incorporated, four per wing. Each EPU consists of an electric motor with its inverter, driving an outboard propeller. All EPUs are connected to an electric bus, which distributes power from the inboard electric machine. Consequently, the total power required from the battery is the sum of the power demands from all components linked to the bus.

To regulate thrust distribution between the inboard and outboard propulsion systems, a split factor ψ is introduced. The thrust produced by each inboard propeller, T_{IB} , and by each outboard propeller, T_{OB} , are defined as:

$$T_{IB} = T_{total} * (1 - \psi)/2 \quad , \quad T_{OB} = T_{total} * \psi/8 \quad (3)$$

For the component models, the performance of the gas turbine is estimated using a surrogate model of the multi-spool turboshaft implemented in pyCycle [19]. This model is then “rubberized” by normalizing the output power and interpolating across simulated altitudes and Mach numbers (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: Engine stage variables for a kerosene multi-spool turboshaft sized at $M = 0.6$, $h = 25000$ ft, and $W_{shp} = 1800$ hp. The lines and curves represent fitted responses, while the markers correspond to the obtained data.

Propeller performance is assessed using a surrogate model generated from XROTOR [20] by producing $J - C_P$ propeller maps. To account for different propeller designs, the propellers are sized at $h = 6000$ m, with a forward velocity of 0.6 M, operating at 800 rpm. Disk loadings range from 286 N/m² to 1145 N/m², represented by a sizing factor ϖ in increments of $\Delta\varpi = 0.25$. This approach allows the optimizer to design propellers capable of operating at higher power coefficients (higher ϖ) at the cost of reduced propeller efficiency η (see Fig. 5).

Clearance constraints are imposed on the propellers to ensure a minimum roll angle of 8° (Ψ_{roll}) and a clearance of 0.1 m for both the inboard and outboard propellers, denoted as $\Delta Clear_{IB}$ and $\Delta Clear_{OB}$, respectively (see ig. 6). For all optimizations, the inboard propeller is assumed to be positioned at $0.25b/2$, while the outboard propellers are equally spaced from $0.5b/2$ to $b/2$.

For the electric components, fixed efficiencies of $\eta = 0.95$ are assumed for the electric motor, inverter, rectifier, and electric machine. These efficiency values were provided by partners from the University of Strathclyde [21]. For the battery, a pack-level specific energy of 350 Wh/kg and a pack-level specific power of 1000 W/kg are assumed, based on projections from [22].

2.1.3 Aircraft weight estimation

For weight estimation, empirical formulas were applied. Wing mass, furnishings, nacelles, landing gear, and horizontal and vertical tail weights were calculated using Raymer's formulas [15], while the fuselage mass was determined using the formula from Torenbeek [18]. All values were corrected based on the weight breakdown of the A320-200 presented in [23]. Additional adjustments for the T-tail were made using weight breakdown data from the ATR42 [23] and ATR72 [24]. To properly account for the effects

Figure 5: Propeller $J - C_P$ maps at different design disk loadings.

Figure 6: Definition of the inboard clearance constraint $\Delta C_{ler_{IB}}$, outboard clearance constraint $\Delta C_{ler_{OB}}$, and roll angle clearance constraint Ψ_{roll}

of aspect ratio, a modified version of Raymer’s dependency on AR was employed, based on second-order fitted curves from [25]. The evolution of the normalized¹ wing weight is illustrated in Fig. 7, showing that the classical Raymer equation tends to underestimate the increase in wing weight with rising AR . For this study, the curve corresponding to the strut-braced CFRP wing will be applied. 5

For the powerplant weight estimation, adjusted specific power values are applied to various components. A specific power of 2.6 kW/kg is considered for the turboshaft dry core and auxiliary systems. For the gearbox, a specific power of 16.4 kW/kg is assumed [26], while electric machines (including electric motors and generators) are assigned a specific power of 15 kW/kg [27]. Additionally, inverters and rectifiers are characterized by a specific power of 23 kW/kg [28]. For the payload, passengers are assumed to be homogeneously distributed across the cabin, occupying all available seats, with an average weight of 75.4 kg [29]. It is further assumed that 1800 kg of luggage is stored in the overhead compartments, with the remaining 4628 kg placed in the lower fuselage cargo compartments.

Additional fudge weights for avionics, power distribution subsystems, and operational

¹With an aspect ratio of $AR = 10$

Figure 7: Tendency of the normalized wing weight for various wing configurations.

items were introduced based on the A320 weight breakdown [23] to accurately adjust the operational empty weight.

2.2 Flight Mission

The model evaluates a nominal mission of 1,200 nm with a 400 nm diversion segment, including a 30-minute holding pattern. A cruise altitude of 6 km and a flight speed of Mach 0.6 are selected for the analysis.

To account for the inherent variability of low-altitude procedures (below 900 m), 10 distinct procedures are incorporated, each with its corresponding initial climb and final descent profiles. These procedures are derived from flight data collected at four European airports: LEBL (Barcelona El Prat), LEMD (Adolfo Suárez Madrid–Barajas), RIX (Riga), and DTM (Dortmund). The selected trajectories were extracted from a dataset generated through extensive research conducted by CRIDA [30], representing the most common flight paths as well as best and worst case scenarios in terms of Local Air Quality (LAQ) and noise impacts. For this study, the most common trajectories were selected along with six additional distinct trajectories to ensure sufficient variability in the analysis.

To ensure trajectory continuity, each low-altitude procedure was integrated with the remainder of the mission by interpolating speed and flight path angles using spline functions. All flight phases are discretized into 10 nodes, and for the multiple-trajectory cases, only the first trajectory is connected to the extended mission. The resulting mission profiles are illustrated in the upper panel of Figure 8, with detailed views of the climb and descent segments shown in the lower panel. This approach introduces a controlled source of uncertainty for low-altitude procedures in the optimization process while maintaining nearly identical cruise segments (the cruise duration varies slightly due to differences in climb and descent durations).

2.2.1 Low-speed failure modes

To adapt the One Engine Inoperative (OEI) condition to the parallel-serial hybrid-electric architecture, five distinct failure cases are considered. For each failure case, the Balanced Field Length (BFL) is calculated following the methodology presented in [31].

- **FC1:** This case involves the simultaneous failure of the left inboard propeller and its adjacent outboard propeller. Despite these failures, the left turboshaft remains

Figure 8: Top three figures: vertical altitude profile, true airspeed profile and flight path angle γ profile for the nominal missions and the extended mission. Bottom four figures: closeup of the TAS and the γ as a function of the altitude for the climb and descent segments.

Figure 9: Failure case scenarios for the hybrid electric powerplant. Controls in red indicate fixed values, controls in black indicate optimization design variables and controls in green indicate state variables.

operational as a turbogenerator at a prescribed gas turbine throttle setting (δ_{gt}), which is treated as a design variable. Consistent with OEI conditions, the right gearbox is working at full power ($\delta_{gb} = 1$), while the outboard electric motor throttle (δ_{em}) remains a design variable. The right gas turbine throttle is determined by the local hybridization factor, which may differ from the nominal hybridization factor under non-failure conditions.

- **FC2:** This case examines the failure of both outermost outboard propeller units, representing the most critical scenario in terms of yawing moment due to asymmetric propulsion. As in FC1, both gearbox throttles are fixed at $\delta_{gb} = 1$, while the remaining outboard propeller throttles are treated as design variables.
- **FC3:** In this scenario, the left gas turbine fails while the inboard propeller remains functional. The left propeller operates at a reduced gearbox throttle (δ_{gb}), treated as a design variable—with power supplied exclusively by the electric machine. The right propulsion system operates with a gearbox throttle fixed at $\delta_{gb} = 1$, while electric motor throttles and the right local hybridization factor are treated as design variables.
- **FC4:** This case simulates the failure of half of the battery pack. Both gearbox throttles are fixed at $\delta_{gb} = 1$, with a new local hybridization factor introduced as a design variable. Outboard electric throttles are also treated as design variables to optimize power distribution under these conditions.
- **FC5:** This case mirrors FC3 but with the failure of the left inboard electric component instead of the gas turbine. The gearbox operates at a reduced throttle (as a design variable), with power provided solely by the turboshaft engine. All other control parameters follow the same methodology as in FC3.

For failure case FC2, the yawing moments produced by asymmetric thrust during the rolling phase were analyzed, along with the maximum counteracting yawing moment achievable with a sideslip angle of $\beta = 10^\circ$ and a rudder deflection of $\delta_r = 10^\circ$. The aerodynamic coefficients for sideforce (C_{Fy}) and yawing moment (C_{Mz}) were derived from a VSPAero regression model incorporating the fuselage, vertical tail, and horizontal tail configurations across various vertical tail areas. To ensure directional controllability during this critical failure mode, a constraint was implemented requiring the aerodynamic moment to exceed the asymmetric thrust moment.

3 THE MDA

The Multidisciplinary Design Analysis (MDA) problem is formulated using a Multidisciplinary Feasible (MDF) architecture, implemented with a fixed-point Gauss-Seidel algorithm. Conceptually, the MDA involves several interrelated disciplines (Fig. 10). First, given the parametric aircraft design variables, the system computes component dimensions, center of mass locations, and component weights, while providing the optimizer with constraint information related to clearances and mass consistency. Next, a BFL analysis is conducted across multiple failure scenarios to determine required take-off distances and evaluate powerplant component performance. This process continues with mission-specific analysis, computing powerplant performance throughout each flight

Figure 10: XDSM of the main performed optimization

Figure 11: MDA performed on each phase of the flight mission

phase. Finally, these mission-specific results are integrated to construct a mean fuel consumption objective function.

Examining the interconnection within aircraft performance disciplines, Fig.11 illustrate the multidisciplinary analysis performed at each flight phase to determine aircraft performance. The analysis begins by calculating aerodynamic coefficients based on the current aircraft geometry and flight conditions. These coefficients are then used to trim the aircraft under steady-state aerodynamic conditions, as described by Eq.4:

$$q \cdot S_{ref} \cdot CL(\alpha, \delta_e) - W \cdot \cos(\gamma) = 0 \quad (4a)$$

$$T_{total} - q \cdot S_{ref} \cdot CD(\alpha, \delta_e) - W \cdot \sin(\gamma) = 0 \quad (4b)$$

$$C_M(\alpha, \delta_e) = 0 \quad (4c)$$

After trimming, the total thrust requirement T_{total} is distributed between the inboard and outboard propellers. A Newton solver determines the input power P required for each propeller to generate the necessary thrust T at the current advance ratio J . At these power requirements feed into the powertrain model, which calculates the powerplant's operating point and provides the fuel mass flow rate \dot{m}_{fuel} and battery discharge rate \dot{SOC} . These

values are integrated and linked to data from previous flight phases. The updated fuel mass is then fed into the center of gravity (CG) calculator, which adjusts the CG position accordingly. The implicit relationship between CG position and aircraft mass affecting aerodynamic coefficients and trim is solved using the Gauss-Seidel method.

For the takeoff analysis, a similar process is employed, with the Gauss-Seidel method now handling the speeds of each segment and the equations of motion being solved with a nested Newton-solver (for more detail see [10]).

4 THE TESTCASES

In this study, three optimization analyses are proposed to investigate the effects of control strategy and the impact of variability in low-altitude procedures:

- **Case 1:** Optimization considering a single mission profile.
- **Case 2:** Optimization considering multiple trajectories under a unified control strategy.
- **Case 3:** Optimization considering multiple trajectories, each with its own trajectory-specific control strategy.

For all analyses, the objective function to be optimized is the average block fuel, representing the fuel consumed to fly the nominal part of the mission. This is expressed as:

$$W_{\text{block fuel,mean}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N W_{\text{block fuel},i} \quad (5)$$

In the case of a single trajectory (Case 1), the mean is computed from a single value.

The design variables for the optimization are presented in Tab. 1 (left). These variables include: Propeller design parameters, such as the diameter, tangential tip Mach number², and disk loading factor; tail surface sizing (vertical and horizontal tail surfaces³); wing characteristics (aspect ratio and its position along the fuselage); powerplant components (power rating, representing the maximum peak power values at which components can operate; and battery weight).

The control variables ψ and HF^* are defined using discrete nodes to ensure consistency across different flight phases. They remain constant during cruise and procedures below 900 m, while varying linearly along the nominal climb and descent segments of the nominal mission profile, as well as throughout the extended mission. For the single-mission optimization (Case 1) and the multiple-mission optimization with unified control (Case 2), a common control profile is applied across all missions. In contrast, for the multiple-mission optimization with customized control (Case 3), individual control profiles are tailored specifically for each nominal mission. For low-speed operations, the control variables are defined to remain constant under All Engines Operative (AEO) conditions, with

²A constraint is enforced over the Mach number obtained with the velocity triangle to ensure the propeller does not exceed the high-transonic regime.

³the aspect ratio and taper ratios for the tail are pre-selected based on configurations similar to the ATR72 and Dash-8 400.

the flexibility to adjust during failure scenarios. When operating under asymmetric conditions during failure cases, additional control variables are introduced: the gas turbine control parameter δ_{gt} for FC1, and the gearbox control parameter δ_{gb} for FC3 and FC5.

The optimization problem includes constraints detailed in Tab. 1 (right). These constraints govern the throttle level δ of each component, defined as the ratio of operating power to power rating. During normal operation, components must maintain 90% throttle (maximum continuous operating power), while reaching 100% during failure scenarios. For gas turbines, throttle calculations account for operating power relative to the maximum available power at the given altitude and operating point. Additional constraints include mass margin, requiring total component weight to remain below MTOW (Eq.6), propeller linear and angular clearances, residual yawing moment $\mathcal{R}(M_z)$, battery state of charge, aircraft aerodynamic static margin, and balanced field length for each failure mode.

$$\text{Mass Margin} = MTOW - \left(\sum_{i \in \text{components}} W_i \right) - W_{\text{fuel}} - W_{\text{PL}} \quad (6)$$

Design variable (units)	Lower	Upper	Constraint (units)	Lower	Upper
IB diameter (m)	1	6	δ gas turbine (-)	—	0.9/1
IB M_{tang} (-)	0.4	0.8	δ gearbox (-)	—	0.9/1
IB factor (-)	0.5	2	δ electric motor (-)	—	0.9/1
OB diameter (m)	1	6	δ inverter (-)	—	0.9/1
OB M_{tang} (-)	0.4	0.8	δ electric machine (-)	—	0.9/1
OB factor (-)	0.5	2	δ battery (-)	—	0.9/1
Sref HTP (m ²)	1	30	Propeller Cp (-)	—	3
Sref VTP (m ²)	17	40	Propeller M_{true} (-)	—	0.85
AR_w (-)	4	26	Clearance IB (m)	0.1	—
nd_w (-)	0.3	0.6	Clearance OB (m)	0.1	—
Turboshaft rating (MW)	1	20	Ψ_{roll} (deg)	10	—
Gearbox rating (MW)	0.05	20	$\mathcal{R}(M_z)$ (N·m)	0.01	—
Elec motor rating (MW)	0.05	20	Mass margin (m)	0.01	—
Inverter rating (MW)	0.05	20	BFL (m)	—	2000
Elec machine rating (MW)	0.05	20	SOC (-)	0.2	1
Battery Weight (kg)	100	20000	Static margin (-)	0.3	—
ψ (-)	0.1	0.9			
HF* (-)	-30	1			
Takeoff δ_{em} (-)	0.1	0.9			
Takeoff HF (-)	-30	1			
FC1 δ_{gt} (-)	0.01	0.99			
FC3 δ_{gb} (-)	0.01	0.99			
FC4 δ_{gb} (-)	0.01	0.99			

Table 1: Design variables and bounds (left), and associated constraints with limits (right). Green values apply across all mission phases following the aforementioned logic. The values in Red implement one value for AEO and one value for each FC. Values in Pink are applied for all phases. Values in Orange apply for each FC.

Case 1 comprises 53 design variables with 2219 constraints. Case 2 retains the same variables but expands to 6719 constraints due to additional powerplant, State of Charge (SOC), and static margin constraints applied across all mission nodes and phases. Case 3 significantly increases complexity to 143 design variables (as control design variables are applied to each nominal mission) while maintaining the 6719 constraints from Case 2.

The selected optimizer is SNOPT (Sparse Nonlinear OPTimizer) [32], is a gradient-based optimization software using Sequential Quadratic Programming (SQP) to solve large-scale, constrained nonlinear problems with sparse gradients; SNOPT it is widely used for MDO applications due to its efficiency and robustness.

5 RESULTS

The optimized aircraft configurations for all three cases are presented in Fig.12, with their technical specifications detailed in Tab.2.

Figure 12: CAD model of the optimized configurations for the three optimization cases.

The three designs exhibit remarkable similarity, with only minor variations in propeller dimensions and electric motor power ratings. This stems primarily from the fact that while low-altitude procedures introduce some variability, the majority of mission parameters remain consistent across all cases. Consequently, the control strategies shown in Fig. 13 demonstrate nearly identical approaches across all scenarios, with the outboard propellers providing additional thrust during climb and contributing approximately 30 – 37% of the thrust during cruise. Meanwhile, the electric machine predominantly functions as a generator, diverting 27 – 34% of the turboshaft power to the electrical system. It is important to note that variations are more pronounced between different cases than between missions within the same case (Case 3), indicating that these differences are primarily driven by the specific aircraft configuration identified by the optimizer rather than mission requirements.

Variables (units)	Single Trajectory	Single Control	Multiple Control
IB diameter (m)	4.8451	4.7568	4.6767
IB Tang Mtip (-)	0.6587	0.6652	0.6515
IB factor (-)	1.021	0.8348	0.9379
OB diameter (m)	2.1850	2.3811	2.558
OB Tang Mtip (-)	0.5426	0.5011	0.553
OB factor (-)	0.7634	0.7601	1.0135
Sref HTP (m ²)	11.5382	11.6815	12.7385
Sref VTP (m ²)	17	17	17
AR_w (-)	22.0134	22.0112	21.9986
nd_w (-)	0.4748	0.4738	0.4715
Turboshaft rating (MW)	5.8761	5.9039	5.8003
Gearbox rating (MW)	4.8147	4.8703	4.6331
Electric power rating (MW)	0.8638	1.121	1.7608
Inverter rating (MW)	0.8589	1.1146	1.8442
Elec machine rating (MW)	2.683	2.5987	2.8199
Battery Weight (kg)	11982.9	11112.5	11040.7
Total fuel (Nom+Ext) (kg)	6638.6	6691.5	6780.11

Table 2: Optimization results for the optimization of the aircraft in the three optimization cases.

Figure 13: Optimized HF^* and ψ controls for the nominal and extended missions for the three optimization cases.

Examining the performance-defining variables across the nominal mission, Fig. 14 (top) illustrates the propeller efficiency η for both inboard and outboard propellers. The results confirm that the optimizer effectively sizes the propellers for cruise efficiency, with only Case 3 exhibiting lower outboard efficiencies due to the selection of a higher thrust-producing outboard propeller design, corresponding to higher cruise split factors ψ .

Figure 14: Aircraft performance variables during nominal mission for the three optimization cases.

Regarding powertrain sizing, Fig.14 (middle) shows that both electric motors and turboshafts are sized to meet the demands of lower-altitude climb procedures, with the turboshaft subsequently operating at approximately $\delta_{gt} \approx 78\%$ during the cruise segment. The battery usage pattern, depicted in Fig.14 (down), illustrates the evolution of the state of charge (SOC), showing similar discharge profiles across all missions.⁴ To quantify the hybrid power distribution, a global hybridization factor is defined as the ratio of battery

⁴With the exception of one mission-specific control case, which appears to be an outlier resulting from optimizer convergence issues, as evidenced by the absence of battery discharge.

power to the total energy provided by both the battery and turboshafts:

$$HF^{global} = \frac{P_{battery}}{P_{battery} + 2P_{gt}} \quad (7)$$

This metric reveals that batteries primarily serve as power-boosting devices, with hybridization factors upwards of 57% during climb, followed by reduced cruise hybridization to approximately 10%.

Figure 15: Block fuel for nominal missions across the three optimization cases. Lower opacity bars for the single mission indicate MDA results using optimized design variables.

Figure 16: Throttles of the gas turbine and electric motors for all the missions using the aircraft and HF^* , ψ control profiles from Case 1.

Finally, considering the effects of multi-mission and mission-specific control, Fig.15 presents the block fuel consumption for the nominal mission across the three optimization cases. As observed, the multi-mission analysis with mission-specific control consistently outperforms the multi-mission approach with a monolithic control strategy, except for the outlier case with undischarged batteries previously identified in Fig.14. This result is expected, as mission-specific controls enable more precise energy management tailored to the constraints of each mission phase. For the single-mission case, an MDA was performed to assess performance across other missions (represented by bars with lower opacity in Fig.14). While the initial analysis may suggest that the single-mission approach

outperforms the multi-mission monolithic control, a detailed examination of powerplant components during the mission reveals that the powerplant operates beyond the designed power limits (Fig.16), underscoring the importance of multi-mission analysis for achieving reliable designs.

	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3
$\mu_{\text{block fuel}}$ (kg)	4448.57	4480.35	4429.07
$\sigma_{\text{block fuel}}$ (kg)	13.03	12.74	6.19

Table 3: Mean and sample standard deviation of nominal block fuel missions.

Examining the performance statistics across the various optimized cases, Tab. 3 presents the mean and standard deviation of each optimization case, excluding the outlier from Case 3. As expected, the multi-mission analysis with mission-specific control outperforms the monolithic control approach in terms of both mean block fuel and deviation, achieving a 1.14% reduction in mean block fuel. While this fuel reduction can be significant over the long term, additional operational uncertainties may diminish these savings, potentially offsetting the benefits of the increased operational complexity.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This paper has shown the application of the in-house MDO software TOPAZ to optimize a high aspect ratio, strut-braced aircraft with hybrid-electric distributed propulsion, considering various mission and sizing scenarios. The findings indicate that multi-mission analysis is essential to achieve a robust design capable of addressing uncertainties associated with low-altitude procedures. While incorporating mission-specific control results in a design with lower mean block fuel, the improvements are minimal. The mission-specific controls provide slight adjustments for each mission, resulting in a mean block fuel reduction of 1.14%.

7 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The activities described in this paper have been carried out under the project INDIGO (Integration and Digital Demonstration of Low-emission Aircraft Technologies and Airport Operations). INDIGO project [4] has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the HorizonEurope programme under grant agreement No 10109605.

REFERENCES

- [1] International Energy Agency. Aviation – Energy System, Transport, 2025. URL <https://www.iea.org/energy-system/transport/aviation>. Last updated on 16 January 2025.
- [2] European Commission. Reducing emissions from aviation, 2025. URL https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/transport/reducing-emissions-aviation_en. Accessed on 2025-02-21.

- [3] International Civil Aviation Organization. Trends in Emissions that affect Climate Change, 2025. URL https://www.icao.int/environmental-protection/Pages/ClimateChange_Trends.aspx. Accessed on 2025-02-21.
- [4] Innovative aircraft and propulsion technologies to improve air quality near airports. URL <https://indigo-sustainableaviation.eu/>.
- [5] F. Gallard, C. Vanaret, D. Guénot, V. Gachelin, R. Lafage, B. Pauwels, P.-J. Barjhoux, and A. Gazaix. Gems: A python library for automation of multidisciplinary design optimization process generation. In *2018 AIAA/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Materials Conference*, 2018.
- [6] B. J. Brelje and J. R. R. A. Martins. Development of a conceptual design model for aircraft electric propulsion with efficient gradients. In *Proceedings of the AIAA/IEEE Electric Aircraft Technologies Symposium*, Cincinnati, OH, July 2018. doi:10.2514/6.2018-4979.
- [7] C. David, S. Delbecq, S. Defoort, P. Schmollgruber, E. Benard, and V. Pommier-Budinger. From fast to fast-oad: An open source framework for rapid overall aircraft design. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 1024(1):012062, jan 2021. doi:10.1088/1757-899X/1024/1/012062. URL <https://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/1024/1/012062>.
- [8] R. Quiben Figueroa, R. Cavallaro, and A. Cini. Feasibility studies on regional aircraft retrofitted with hybrid-electric powertrains. *Aerospace Science and Technology*, 151: 109246, Aug. 2024. ISSN 1270-9638. doi:10.1016/j.ast.2024.109246.
- [9] J. Gratz, J. Jasa, E. Aretskin-Hariton, K. Moore, K. Marfatia, J. Kirk, and C. Recine. Aviary: An Open-Source Multidisciplinary Design, Analysis, and Optimization Tool for Modeling Aircraft with Analytic Gradients. In *AIAA Aviation Forum*, Las Vegas, NV, United States, July 2024. American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics. URL <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/citations/20240007608>. NASA Document ID: 20240007608. Public Use Permitted.
- [10] P. N. Simon, R. Q. Figueroa, A. Cini, and R. Cavallaro. *Multidisciplinary Design and Optimization of H2-Powered Regional Aircraft Architectures*. doi:10.2514/6.2025-0360. URL <https://arc.aiaa.org/doi/abs/10.2514/6.2025-0360>.
- [11] J. Bradbury, R. Frostig, P. Hawkins, M. J. Johnson, C. Leary, D. Maclaurin, G. Necula, A. Paszke, J. VanderPlas, S. Wanderman-Milne, and Q. Zhang. JAX: composable transformations of Python+NumPy programs, 2018. URL <http://github.com/google/jax>.
- [12] Airbus S.A.S. *A320 Aircraft Characteristics – Airport and Maintenance Planning*. Airbus Customer Services, Technical Data Support and Services, 31707 Blagnac Cedex, France, revision no. 44 edition, June 2024. Originally issued Sep 30, 1985. Proprietary document intended for planning purposes.

- [13] R. A. McDonald and J. R. Gloude-mans. *Open Vehicle Sketch Pad: An Open Source Parametric Geometry and Analysis Tool for Conceptual Aircraft Design*. doi:10.2514/6.2022-0004. URL <https://arc.aiaa.org/doi/abs/10.2514/6.2022-0004>.
- [14] R. D. Finck. USAF Stability and Control DATCOM. Technical Report AF33(616)-6460, F33615-76-C-3061, McDonnell Douglas Corporation, Douglas Aircraft Division, Wright-Patterson Air Force Base, Ohio, April 1978. Originally published October 1960. Revised April 1978. Project No. 8219, Task No. 821901.
- [15] D. P. Raymer. *Aircraft design: A conceptual approach*. AIAA education series. American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Reston, Va., 2006. ISBN 1563478293. URL <http://www.loc.gov/catdir/toc/ecip068/2006004706.html>.
- [16] D. Howe. *Basic Lift, Drag and Mass Representations*, chapter 6, pages 139–164. John Wiley and Sons, Ltd, 2000. ISBN 9781118903094. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118903094.ch6>. URL <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/9781118903094.ch6>.
- [17] M. H. Sadraey. *Aircraft design: A systems engineering approach*. Aerospace Series. John Wiley and Sons, Chichester, 2013. ISBN 9781118352700. doi:10.1002/9781118352700. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/9781118352700>.
- [18] E. Torenbeek. *Synthesis of Subsonic Airplane Design*. Delft University Press, Delft, 1988.
- [19] E. S. Hendricks and J. S. Gray. pycycle: A tool for efficient optimization of gas turbine engine cycles. *Aerospace*, 6(87), August 2019. doi:10.3390/aerospace6080087.
- [20] M. Drela and H. Youngren. XROTOR: An interactive program for the design and analysis of ducted and free-tip propellers and windmills. <https://web.mit.edu/drela/Public/web/xrotor/>, 2022. URL <https://web.mit.edu/drela/Public/web/xrotor/>. Version 7.69, Accessed: 2025-03-31.
- [21] K. F. P. N. C. Jones. Safety-driven baseline of hybrid electric aircraft electrical power system architectures. In *ICAS Proceedings: 34th Congress of the International Council of the Aeronautical Sciences*, number ICAS2024_027, Florence, Italy, October 2024. ICAS.
- [22] H. Kühnelt, F. Mastropierro, N. Zhang, S. Toghyani, and U. Krewer. Are batteries fit for hybrid-electric regional aircraft? *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2526(1):012026, jun 2023. doi:10.1088/1742-6596/2526/1/012026. URL <https://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2526/1/012026>.
- [23] E. Obert. *Aerodynamic design of transport aircraft*. IOS Press, Netherlands, 2009. ISBN 978-1-58603-970-7.
- [24] L. Attanasio, A. De Marco, F. Nicolosi, and P. Vecchia. Development of a java-based framework for aircraft preliminary design and optimization. 06 2015. doi:10.2514/6.2015-2651.

- [25] G. P. Chiozzotto. Conceptual design method for the wing weight estimation of strut-braced wing aircraft. In *5th CEAS Air & Space Conference*, Delft, The Netherlands, September 2015. URL <https://elib.dlr.de/98248/>. Conference presentation; full text not available from repository.
- [26] *Next Generation Turboprop Gearboxes*, volume Volume 2: Aircraft Engine; Marine; Microturbines and Small Turbomachinery of *Turbo Expo*, 04 1982. doi:10.1115/82-GT-236. URL <https://doi.org/10.1115/82-GT-236>.
- [27] C. L. Pastra, C. Hall, G. Cinar, J. Gladin, and D. N. Mavris. Specific power and efficiency projections of electric machines and circuit protection exploration for aircraft applications. In *2022 IEEE Transportation Electrification Conference & Expo (ITEC)*, pages 766–771, 2022. doi:10.1109/ITEC53557.2022.9813927.
- [28] C. Hall, C. L. Pastra, A. Burrell, J. Gladin, and D. N. Mavris. Projecting power converter specific power through 2050 for aerospace applications. In *2022 IEEE Transportation Electrification Conference & Expo (ITEC)*, pages 760–765, 2022. doi:10.1109/ITEC53557.2022.9813991.
- [29] H. Berg, P. Macedo, B. Picinatti, M. Adler, S. Pel, and K. Jacobs. Review of standard passenger weights: Final report. Technical report, Lufthansa Consulting GmbH and SEO Amsterdam Economics, Frankfurt/M., Germany, September 2022. Report submitted to the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) under Contract Reference EASA.2021.C24.
- [30] D. Zheng Zhang, D. Gómez López, J. A. López Sánchez, C. Xia, X. Wang, and A. García Fernández. Local air quality and noise assessment for landing and take-off operations in future airport environment. *Engineering Proceedings*, 90(1), 2025. ISSN 2673-4591. doi:10.3390/engproc2025090074. URL <https://www.mdpi.com/2673-4591/90/1/74>.
- [31] P. Norczyk and R. Cavallaro. *Local Air Quality and Noise Improvements via Optimization of Strut-Braced Wings with Distributed Electric Propulsion*. doi:10.2514/6.2025-0456. URL <https://arc.aiaa.org/doi/abs/10.2514/6.2025-0456>.
- [32] P. E. Gill, W. Murray, and M. A. Saunders. Snopt: An sqp algorithm for large-scale constrained optimization. *SIAM Journal on Optimization*, 12(4):979–1006, 2002. doi:10.1137/S1052623499350013. URL <https://doi.org/10.1137/S1052623499350013>.